

Damage Analysis of Laminates Under Cyclic Loading

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ABSTRACT

The stochastic mesomechanics model developed by the authors for damage accumulation analysis of laminated composites is modified and applied for predicting laminate behavior under cyclic loading. The model is based on a theory of excursions of random process beyond the bounds. Stochastic strains in the laminate subjected to random Gaussian in-plane loading are calculated using lamination theory and random functions theory. Probabilistic variation of stiffness and strength characteristics of a ply-level mesovolume is used in the analysis. Stochastic version of maximum strain failure criterion is applied for damage probability calculation. A mesovolume concept is utilized in modeling the stiffness degradation. The unloading model is merely based on the experimentally observed behavior. Predictions of damage accumulation and failure in a Kevlar/epoxy $[0/\pm 30/90]$ laminate under low-cycle tensile loading are analyzed. Effects of load amplitude, deviation and frequency on damage evolution and number of cycles to failure are discussed. Model predicts three stages of damage accumulation process in laminate under cyclic loading, i.e. initial damage formation, steady damage accumulation, and final failure development. The observed frequency effect on the life time and number of cycles to failure is consistent with existing experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

Behavior of materials under cyclic loads is of great importance for structural applications. It is well-known that, subjected to cyclic loading, materials may fail even though the maximum stress does not exceed the ultimate static strength [1,2]. Fatigue of advanced laminated composites has been studied in numerous experimental works ([3-6] and references therein). Though many aspects of this complicated phenomenon are not yet fully understood, it is known that laminates under repeated loading exhibit progressive accumulation of damages of different type up to the final failure of a material.

Deformation and failure processes in composites are of stochastic nature. It is due to a number of factors, such as scatters in stiffness and strength properties of components, initial geometric and structural imperfections, as well as loading randomness [1,7]. A statistical model for damage accumulation in laminates with random material properties subjected to random monotonically increasing loads was developed in [8-11]. The model is based upon the concept of damage accumulation as a result of random excursions of fluctuating strains in plies beyond

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the static failure strain bounds. The method predicts gradual damage accumulation and deformation history of composite laminates.

In this paper, an attempt is made to modify approach [8-11] in order to describe damage evolution in laminates subjected to cyclic loading. The damage accumulation in a Kevlar/epoxy [0/±30/90]_s laminate under low-cycle tensile loading is analyzed. Effects of loading amplitude, deviation, and frequency are discussed.

STOCHASTIC DAMAGE ACCUMULATION MODEL

Consider symmetric laminate consisting of unidirectionally reinforced laminas with initial random elastic characteristics $\bar{E}_{1_0}^k, \bar{E}_{2_0}^k, \bar{G}_{12_0}^k, \bar{\nu}_{12_0}^k$. Index k stands for ply number. Assume the normal distribution of laminas properties, hence they can be described by mathematical expectations $\bar{E}_{1_0}^k, \bar{E}_{2_0}^k, \bar{G}_{12_0}^k, \bar{\nu}_{12_0}^k$ and dispersions $D_{E_{1_0}}, D_{E_{2_0}}, D_{G_{12_0}}, D_{\nu_{12_0}}$. Laminate lay-up is given by ply orientation angles α^k . Then laminate effective properties can be calculated using lamination theory and linearized theory of functions of random variables [8].

Load applied to such a laminate results in random stress-strain field in each ply. Assume that the stresses applied $\tilde{\sigma}_i(t) = [\tilde{\sigma}_{11}(t), \tilde{\sigma}_{22}(t), \tilde{\tau}_{12}(t)]$ are independent differentiable Gaussian processes of time, i. e. they can be described by mathematical expectations $\bar{\sigma}_i(t)$ and correlation functions $K_{\sigma_i}(t_1, t_2)$. Assume further that $\tilde{\sigma}_i(t)$ are quasi stationary cyclic processes, i.e. their mathematical expectations are slow periodic functions of time and correlation functions depend only on time difference $K_{\sigma_i}(t_1, t_2) = K_{\sigma_i}(t_2 - t_1) = K_{\sigma_i}(\delta)$. Therefore, the derivatives of stresses will also be quasi-stationary processes with mathematical expectations and correlation functions defined as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\dot{\sigma}}_i(t) &= \dot{\bar{\sigma}}_i(t) \\ K_{\dot{\sigma}_i}(\delta) &= -\frac{d^2}{d\delta^2} K_{\sigma_i}(\delta) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Assume that the processes of changing the composite compliances are slow and their derivatives may be neglected. Then the mathematical expectations and dispersions of laminate deformations and deformation derivatives can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\epsilon}_i(t) &= \int_0^t \bar{S}_{ij}(\tau) \bar{\dot{\sigma}}_j(\tau) d\tau \\ \bar{\dot{\epsilon}}_i(t) &= \bar{S}_{ij}(t) \bar{\dot{\sigma}}_j(t) \\ D_{\epsilon_i} &= \bar{S}_{ij}^2(t) K_{\sigma_j}(0) + \bar{\sigma}_j^2(t) D_{S_{ij}} \\ D_{\dot{\epsilon}_i} &= \bar{S}_{ij}^2(t) K_{\dot{\sigma}_j}(0) + D_{S_{ij}} (\bar{\dot{\sigma}}_j(t))^2 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where, $\bar{S}_{ij}(t)$ are current laminate compliances. Random strain functions in plies $\tilde{\epsilon}_i^k(t)$ can be calculated using lamination theory and current laminas properties [9].

The probability of excursion of strains $\tilde{\epsilon}_i^k(t)$ beyond the limits $\tilde{\epsilon}_i^k, \tilde{\epsilon}_i^k$, where the $\tilde{\epsilon}_i^k$ (in tension) and $\tilde{\epsilon}_i^k$ (in compression) bounds are random in general can be calculated as

$$r_i^k(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_0^t v_i^k(\tau) d\tau\right) \quad (3)$$

where $v_i^k(t)$ is mathematical expectation of number of excursions per unit time. Under the assumption of statistical independence of negative and positive excursions, $v_i^k(t)$ is a sum of these two numbers

$$v_i^k(t) = v_{i-}^k(t) + v_{i+}^k(t) \quad (4)$$

Mathematical expectation of mean number of excursions can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{i-}^k(t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{D_{\epsilon_i}}{D_{\epsilon_i} + D_{\epsilon_{i-}^k}}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\bar{\epsilon}_i(t) - \bar{\epsilon}_{i-}^k)^2}{2(D_{\epsilon_i} + D_{\epsilon_{i-}^k})}\right) \times \left\{ \exp\left(-\frac{\bar{\epsilon}_i(t)^2}{2D_{\epsilon_i}}\right) - \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{D_{\epsilon_i}}} \bar{\epsilon}_i(t) \Phi\left(-\frac{\bar{\epsilon}_i(t)}{\sqrt{D_{\epsilon_i}}}\right) \right\} \\ v_{i+}^k(t) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{D_{\epsilon_i}}{D_{\epsilon_i} + D_{\epsilon_{i+}^k}}} \exp\left(-\frac{(\bar{\epsilon}_i(t) - \bar{\epsilon}_{i+}^k)^2}{2(D_{\epsilon_i} + D_{\epsilon_{i+}^k})}\right) \times \left\{ \exp\left(-\frac{\bar{\epsilon}_i(t)^2}{2D_{\epsilon_i}}\right) + \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{D_{\epsilon_i}}} \bar{\epsilon}_i(t) \left[1 - \Phi\left(-\frac{\bar{\epsilon}_i(t)}{\sqrt{D_{\epsilon_i}}}\right)\right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where, $\Phi(U) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^U e^{-\frac{u^2}{2}} du = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \operatorname{erf}\left(\frac{U}{\sqrt{2}}\right)\right]$ is Laplace function; the ply index k is avoided for simplicity.

In order to use the information about the failure probabilities (3), we need to specify how is it utilized in the composite, i. e. when and how much damages of different types do emerge and how do they affect the current mechanical properties of laminate. Assume that there are three types of damages related to three in-plane deformations in each ply $\epsilon_i^k = [\epsilon_{11}^k, \epsilon_{22}^k, \epsilon_{12}^k]$. Failure type due to ϵ_{11}^k exceeding the critical bounds can be associated with fiber breakage, and those due to ϵ_{22}^k and ϵ_{12}^k - with matrix and interface cracking in transverse direction and in shear, respectively.

Assume that each ply consists of certain number of mesovolumes. The mesovolume has to be structurally homogeneous, i.e. to contain sufficient amount of reinforcing fibers as to be considered as a continuum, and at the same time it has to be comparatively small in order to satisfy the condition of stochastic homogeneity of stress and strain fields inside its envelope. Initial random characteristics of plies are equal to respective mesovolumes characteristics. Assume that each of the mesovolumes can be either perfect or broken in any of three ways, namely in fiber direction, in transverse direction and in shear. We suppose that at every current state of loading, the relative fractions of broken mesovolumes in plies for each type of failure are proportional to probabilities of failure r_i^k . Based upon this mesovolume concept the stiffness degradation model was proposed in [8] as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{E}_1^k(\tau) &= \bar{E}_{10}^k (1 - r_{11}^k(\tau)) & \bar{E}_2^k(\tau) &= \bar{E}_{20}^k (1 - r_{22}^k(\tau)) \\ \bar{G}_{12}^k(\tau) &= \bar{G}_{120}^k (1 - r_{12}^k(\tau)) & \bar{\nu}_{12}^k(\tau) &= \bar{\nu}_{120}^k (1 - r_{11}^k(\tau)) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The relative standard deviations were assumed to remain constant. According to this algorithm damage accumulation in plies evokes the shift of plies moduli distributions towards zero direction and narrows these distributions proportionally to stiffness decrease. This simple approach does not take into consideration micromechanical phenomena like stress redistribution around the single cracks or cracks interaction, but does describe gradual stiffness reduction due to damage in plies and stress redistribution between plies.

In order to apply this model to analyze laminates under cyclic loading, certain experimental observations of the behavior of brittle materials under loading and unloading are implemented. The necessary modifications to the model closely follow observations made by Hahn and Kim [4] while studying the hysteresis in laminates. They observed residual deformation after unloading that disappeared in short time implying a viscoelastic behavior. They attributed stiffness reduction to damage accumulation. The modifications to the model do not describe viscoelastic effects, but allow to analyze damage accumulation and stiffness reduction of laminates as well as the contribution to hysteresis due to damage formation. It is assumed that the damage accumulation takes place only during the increasing-load-portion of each loading cycle. New damage does not appear during the unloading and a laminate responds to load according to the effective secant moduli at the peak load. At the beginning of next cycle, damages start to accumulate again and laminate response follows current effective moduli, taking into account all damages accumulated during previous cycles. It should be pointed out that the stochastic process based arguments utilized for the modelling of loading of laminates are not capable of interpreting the observed unloading behavior of these materials.

A computer code is developed for calculating laminate response using the above described approach. Incremental loading is set according to given stress derivatives $\bar{\sigma}_i(t)$ and deformation integral (2) is integrated numerically during loading portion of each cycle. After the peak is reached, laminate strains are set to zero and the calculation for the loading portion of the next cycle is initiated. At each time step during loading damage functions $r_i^k(t)$ are used to calculate the current elastic properties of laminate. It is shown [9] that sufficiently small load increments should be taken in order to ensure stability of numerical integration. In case of cyclic loading, a large load increment with the iteration procedure [8] is utilized. Damage functions are iteratively calculated at the same loading step until they do not change during two subsequent iterations. It is assumed that final failure occurs when any of the current effective laminate moduli $\bar{E}_1(t)$, $\bar{E}_2(t)$, or $\bar{G}_{12}(t)$ becomes equal to zero. The calculated information for each time step is appended to the data file, including the information on laminate stresses, strains, and lamina strains, the damage content $r_i^k(t)$ in plies, the average content of damages of different type in the laminate $r_i(t) = [\sum_{k=1}^n r_i^k(t)]/n$, the cumulative damage content $r_c(t) = [\sum_{i=1}^3 r_i(t)]/3$, and the current laminate elastic moduli $\bar{E}_1(t)$, $\bar{E}_2(t)$, $\bar{G}_{12}(t)$. The program is written in "Mathematica" language.

APPLICATIONS

The model is utilized for predicting the cyclic damage accumulation in Kevlar/epoxy [0/±30/90]_s laminate under tension. Experimental statistical data for Kevlar/epoxy unidirectional composite are used in the calculation [8]. The mathematical expectation (mean) $\bar{\sigma}_{11}(t)$ of loading process $\tilde{\sigma}_{11}(t)$ is periodic triangular function of time and correlation function is

$$K_{\sigma}(\delta) = \sigma_q^2 e^{-\delta^2/\tau_0^2} \quad (7)$$

where, $\sigma_q^2 = D_{\sigma} = K_{\sigma}(0)$ is dispersion of process, and τ_0 is autocorrelation time of random fluctuations of loading. The derivative $\dot{\tilde{\sigma}}_{11}(t)$, consequently, has piecewise constant mathematical expectation of alternate sign and dispersion $D_{\dot{\sigma}} = K_{\dot{\sigma}}(0) = 2\sigma_q^2/\tau_0^2$. Load amplitude in the following analysis is defined as a fraction of laminate ultimate strength $\sigma_{ult} = 705$ MPa under monotonic deterministic tensile loading, obtained by the model [8]. The loading frequency is

equal to $0.1\tau_0^{-1}$ throughout numerical study, except for the frequency effect analysis. This corresponds to period $T = 10\tau_0$.

DAMAGE ACCUMULATION UNDER CYCLIC LOADING

Figure 1 shows deformation response of $[0/\pm 30/90]_s$ laminate to cyclic tensile loading at loading amplitude 0.65 and loading deviation $\sigma_q = 5$ MPa. Variations of damage functions r_i^k in plies and average damage functions r_i are shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows cumulative damage r_c formation in the laminate as well as laminate effective moduli degradation under cyclic loading. In these and following figures continuous lines, dashed lines, and dash-dot lines correspond to 11, 22, and 12 components of variables, respectively, if the opposite is not stated.

FIGURE 1. Mean cyclic deformations (a) and stress-strain diagrams (b) under tension: loading amplitude - 0.65, deviation - 5 MPa

Analysis shows that matrix transverse cracks occur first in the 90 degree ply (Figure 2c). It is interesting that applied load amplitude exceeds the stress range of transverse crack formation in this ply under deterministic loading. However, when loading function is a stochastic process of time, effects of loading rate and time spent at a given loading level are as important as loading level itself [10,11]. In this particular case of loading it took three cycles to complete matrix transverse damage formation in 90 degree ply. Shear damage in ± 30 plies start to accumulate from the first cycle and accumulates with almost uniform rate till 80% of total life time (Figure 2b). Fiber breakage develops slowly in 0 and 90 plies in tensile and compressive mode, respectively. Only after sufficient amount of damages is accumulated, fibers start to break rapidly, first in 90 degree ply at about 50% of life time (Figure 2c), and then in 0 degree ply (Figure 2a) which leads to the final failure of laminate. Cumulative damage formation (Figure 3a) by analogy with [12] can be subdivided into three characteristic regions. First stage lasts two cycles and represents initial damage formation in the laminate. Second stage exhibits almost uniform damage accumulation during three consecutive cycles. And finally, third stage covering last three cycles, reveals rapid increase of damage content of different types leading to the final failure of the laminate. At this stage, damages in adjacent plies interact with each other through stress redistribution between the plies. Changes in deformation and stiffness are not significant in the first two stages (Figures 1a and 3b). Discernible damage induced hysteresis in stress-strain diagrams (Figure 1b) is also seen in the third stage only.

FIGURE 2. Damage formation in plies 0 (a), ± 30 (b), 90 (c), and average damage (d)

FIGURE 3. Cumulative damage function (a) and laminate moduli degradation (b)

EFFECT OF LOADING AMPLITUDE

Average fiber, transverse matrix, and shear damage functions as well as cumulative damage function are shown in Figure 4 for four different loading amplitudes. Loading deviation in all cases is 5 MPa. Tensile moduli degradation is shown in Figure 5. It is seen that the increase of loading amplitude decreases laminate life under cyclic loading. For loading level 0.8 and

given deviation laminate fails at the end of the second loading cycle. Decrease of loading amplitude from 0.65 to 0.6 almost triples laminate life time. Analysis of cumulative damage curves (Figure 4d) shows that three damage accumulation stages discussed above become more pronounced for lower loads. The interval of uniform damage accumulation (second stage) becomes substantially larger, when initial damage accumulation interval grows relatively slowly and final failure interval remains practically unchanged with amplitude decrease. The same damage accumulation stages are revealed on moduli degradation (Figure 5).

FIGURE 4. Average fiber (a), transverse (b), and shear matrix (c) damage, and cumulative damage function (d): numbers indicate loading amplitudes

FIGURE 5. Laminate axial (a) and transverse (b) moduli degradation: numbers indicate loading amplitudes

EFFECT OF LOADING DEVIATION

Figure 6a shows cumulative damage functions for four loading deviations. Loading amplitude is 0.65. It is seen that loading deviation affects essentially both damage accumulation and time to failure at a given load amplitude. Increase in deviation from 1 to 15 MPa decreases laminate life time almost threefold. At higher deviations, three stages in damage accumulation process discussed above are less pronounced. Decrease in deviation increases time intervals of initial damage formation and steady damage accumulation. Figure 6b shows the variation of loading amplitude with number of cycles to failure for four loading deviations. It is seen that the high loading deviation results in larger number of cycles to failure at high loading amplitudes above a certain loading level (0.73 in Figure 6b). However, below this loading level a higher loading deviation results in a lower number of cycles to failure. This effect is analogous to the effect of loading deviation on laminate strength at various loading rates [9,10].

FIGURE 6. Cumulative damage functions (a) and variation of loading amplitude with the number of cycles-to-failure (b): numbers indicate loading deviation in MPa

EFFECT OF FREQUENCY

Figure 7a shows cumulative damage functions due to cyclic tensile loading at four different frequencies. Loading amplitude is 0.65, loading deviation is 5 MPa. It is seen that decrease in loading frequency (or increase of period) causes increase of damage accumulation per cycle and lowers number of cycles to failure. This effect has been observed experimentally in fatigue of advanced composites [13,14] and is associated usually with the fact that at lower frequency laminate is subjected to loading during longer period of time per cycle. It may be suggested then that time-to-failure is not sensitive to frequency. Results presented in Figure 7b show, however, the frequency effect. The reason for frequency dependence of time-to-failure is the variation of damage accumulation rate with loading rate. Lowering frequency at constant amplitude lowers strain rate and consequently decreases the number of excursions per unit time (5).

Figure 8 shows variation of number of cycles and time to failure with loading frequency for several loading amplitudes and deviations. For all combinations of loading parameters, decrease of frequency decreases number of cycles to failure and increases time to failure. Frequency effect is more pronounced when loading amplitude and deviation are lower. For 15 MPa deviation (dashed lines in Figure 8), frequency affects the number of cycles to failure whereas time-to-failure remains relatively unchanged. It is because at higher deviations the probability of excursions depend less on loading rate but more on loading level. For lower deviations both cycles and time to failure are frequency dependent. At high frequencies the saturation of variation of number of cycles-to-failure is seen in Figure 8a (solid lines). It is due to the saturation

of rate dependence of probability of excursions, discussed in [9,10]. Calculated variations of time-to-failure with frequency (Figure 8b) correspond qualitatively to experimental data [15] for laminated composites.

FIGURE 7. Cumulative damage variation with loading cycles (a) and time (b); numbers indicate loading frequency in τ_0^{-1}

FIGURE 8. Variation of number of cycles to failure (a) and time to failure (b) with loading frequency; loading deviation 5 MPa (solid lines) and 15 MPa (dashed lines); numbers in legend indicate loading amplitude

CONCLUSIONS

Stochastic mesomechanics model developed by the authors is modified for cyclic damage accumulation and life prediction. The modifications are based on the experimentally observed behavior. Effects of loading amplitude, deviation, and frequency are analyzed. The results show that cyclic damage accumulation process may be subdivided into three stages, namely initial damage formation, steady damage accumulation, and final failure. The relative duration of these stages may change under different loading conditions. It is found that frequency of loading affects both number of cycles and time-to-failure of laminate. Frequency effects qualitatively agree with existing experimental data. This is the first attempt to apply the stochastic mesomechanics based model to study the damage accumulation in composites subjected to cyclic loading. The healing process in modelling the unloading portion of the cyclic loading is being studied at present. The results will be presented elsewhere in the near future.

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